

**THE EFFECTS OF PRE-READING ACTIVITIES ON ESP READING
COMPREHENSION**

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Annotation: This article deals with valuable information about role of pre-reading activities in the ESP classroom. The work displays that the activities as pre-reading are effective to foster learners' reading skill. Moreover, the article interprets learners' experiences on reading comprehension through pre reading activities in classroom language learning.

Key words: *cognitive, thinking process, educational contexts, reading comprehension, language preparation, decoding skills, teaching strategies.*

It is obvious that language as means for communication takes an important role in our daily activities. In this modern era, people are demanded to acquire more than one language. One of the important languages that should be mastered is English. But, students usually difficult to express their ideas in English. So, the teachers have to find out the appropriate method for teaching English skills. As we know gain full English knowledge coves four main parts: Reading, writing, speaking and listening. Now we will talk about one of the important skill of English language. Reading English is an important part of language learning because it helps you develop other related skills like grammar, vocabulary, and writing.

Reading is for many people, an enjoyable, intense and private activity, from which much pleasure can be derived, and in which one can become totally absorbed. Reading is private. It is a mental, or cognitive, process which involves a reader in trying to follow and respond to a message from a writer who is distant in space and time. Because of this privacy, the process of reading, the first think that we must know is reading habits. This ability is very important for being good reader. Reading is usually the third language skill that we learn, reading is the way of looking at order the sign of written and become meaningful from them. Reading allows language learners to explore topics that they love and stories that engage them. Reading, even at a slow pace exposes students to more sentences, grammar, and new vocabulary per minute than the average, short class, TV show, or song. This is why students who read foreign books are able to speak more fluently than students who don't, despite having done the same amount of classes.

Generally, reading is a communication process requiring a series of skills, such as reading is a thinking process rather than an exercise in eye movements[1]. Based on the definition above, that reader's knowledge of the world depends on lived experience. This is different in different countries, regions and cultures. H. Douglas Brown said that reading is likewise a skill that teachers simply expect learners to acquire. Reading arguably the most essential skill for success in all educational contexts. According to J. Charles reading is both process and product, the process of reading involves the interaction between the reader and the text-how the reader is deciphering the writing on the page, what he or she is thinking about while reading and reader is monitoring his or her reading. A reader reads a text to understand its meaning, as well as to put that understanding to use. A person reads a text to learn, to find out information, to be entertained, to reflect or as religious practice. The purpose of reading is closely connected to person's motivation to read. It will also affect the way a book is read. We read a dictionary in a different way from the way we read a novel. In the classroom, teachers need to be aware of their students' learning needs.

The reading skill is the most important skill in language. In this sense, teachers have great importance role to increase learners' reading comprehension. To achieve this, teachers use reading activities and strategies when they teach reading in reading class[2]. Based on this discussion; reading comprehension can be achieved by means of reading activities in reading instruction. Reading activities play an important role in reading comprehension for creating and constructing the meaning in written text.

Pre reading stage focuses on knowledge and experience of the reader. In order to activate background knowledge and experience of the reader; researchers give importance especially pre reading phase. In pre reading phase teachers introduce topic by means of pre reading activities. Students' background and existing knowledge can be activated by pre reading activities so in this sense students can acquire new information and construct the meaning in the target reading text. There is a general agreement that teachers build and activate background knowledge in pre reading phase. Pre reading tasks focus on students' attention to a text and students make predictions on the text content by activating their prior knowledge in this sense pre reading activities are related with background knowledge and teachers can build new knowledge and activate background knowledge by means of pre reading activities. Pre reading stage breaks readers' barrier and reader can engage in reading in other words this stage increases reader's interest and motivation, so teachers can activate students' background knowledge in target text. Based on this discussion students can familiarize the topic and prepare the reading text by means

of pre reading activities. Pre reading stage focuses on students' background knowledge, language preparation, and motivation of the learners.

Students generate new ideas and opinions and students develop their cognitive skills while they are generating ideas related to topic. In pre reading stage previewing and predicting activities are also used by the researcher; students look at the title, headings and pictures and students read the first and last paragraph in this activity; and students activate their background knowledge and students are getting familiar too the topic before reading. In while reading stage making prediction, making use of context or guessing, and breaking words into their component parts, paraphrasing activities are used in this study, these activities are used because these activities focus on content of the text and decoding skills. In post reading stage group discussion is used, in group discussion students focus on information in the text and they evaluate and analyze their comprehension in this stage[3].

Studies of pre-reading activities for native speakers have demonstrated the facilitative effects of activating reader's prior knowledge relevant to understanding of the new text. Not only do pre-reading activities prepare native speakers for the concepts that follow, but making the reading task easier and connecting the new concept more meaningfully to prior knowledge, pre-reading activities make reading a more enjoyable task. Pre-reading activities are thus intended to activate appropriate knowledge structures or provide knowledge that the reader lacks. The present study intends to investigate the effects of pre-reading activities on comprehension of engineering students. It is hypothesized that employing the pre-reading activities would significantly improve student;s ability in comprehension. For the realization of this objective two groups of participants were employed and put in the two experimental and control groups. The comparison of mean scores made by subjects of the two groups provided evidence to the effect that whether the difference between teaching strategies, if any, were due to experimental treatment or sampling error.

Young points out that pre-reading activities address "cognitive, linguistic and affective goals". Learners share ideas and experiences, think critically about a topic to be read and come across new vocabulary and structures to be found in the text. The examples of pre-reading activities into six sections: visuals, titles and phrases, songs and dialogues, stories, text-based tasks and games. Rather than dividing the list into the type of cognitive, linguistic or affective skill it addresses (such as predicting, previewing, vocabulary pre-teaching and so on) the list is divided into types of materials used which allows for easier access.

The most simple and recurrent activity with pictures involves asking learners what they

see in the picture or pictures and describing it or them. It is an activity which mostly focuses on creating a context and exploiting vocabulary by recollection or introduction[4]. Prediction can appear when we ask learners to imagine what could be beyond the picture or what they would add to the picture, and so on. A good way of stimulating prediction is covering some parts of the picture and asking learners what they expect to encounter. Another way of achieving this would be to show the picture out of focus and ask learners what they expect to see or yet again show a black and white picture and ask them what colours they would paint it. An activity that also prompts prediction involves learners imagining a story through one or more pictures. It is also possible to use several titles around a picture and ask learners what title they think fits the picture. One thing that should be taken into consideration when carrying out these predictive activities is to let learners formulate as many hypotheses as they can by accepting all their answers as a possibility.

The goals of pre-reading stage are to activate the student's knowledge of the subject, to provide any language preparation that might be needed for coping with the passage and, finally to motivate the learners to want to read the text. Tudor call pre-reading activities "enabling activities" because they provide a reader with the necessary background to organize activity and to comprehend the material (these experiences involve understanding the purpose (S) for reading and building a knowledge base necessary for dealing with the content and the structure of the material). They say that pre-reading activities elicit prior knowledge, and focus attention. Various techniques have been suggested by some authors to mobilize existing knowledge including the use of pictures, movies and even role – plays. Research has not determined which of these is the most effective. So teachers are free to experiment according to the nature of reading material and inclinations of their classes. In an academic setting, however, more formal techniques might be appropriate, of course different scholars listed different types of pre-reading activities, suggests, Word Association, Discussion and Text Surveys.

To sum up all given facts above it should be noted that reading is an active skill. As mentioned earlier, it constantly involves guessing, predicting, checking and asking oneself questions. This should therefore be taken into consideration when devising reading comprehension exercises. It is possible, for instance, to develop the students' powers of inference through systematic practice, or introduce questions which encourage students to anticipate the content of a text from its title and illustrations or the end of a story from the preceding paragraphs. Reading skill is the most important matter of involving appropriate, efficient comprehension strategies. Some students think that in English language is very difficult for

them, because it is not their native language.

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